

LEXICOGRAPHY

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Summary: Stylistic awareness of the discursal properties of Pus is also important in such pragmatic areas as compilation of dictionaries and glossaries, as well as making notes and comments on literary texts. It is of crucial importance to reassess this area of applied stylistics in the light of a discourse-based stylistic approach to language. First I would like to explore a number of challenges in lexicography caused by instantial use.

Making dictionaries is hard and painstaking work; thus it is only natural that lexicographical errors occur even in well-researched and meticulous publications. Lexicographers have to identify the base form and differentiate not only between variants, synonyms, and homonyms, but also between core use and instantial use.

Key words: Failure to identify the base form, failure to identify the etymology of the PU, failure fully or partly to record instantial use.

Failure to identify the base form:

Errors in establishing the base form and the true origin of the PU are frequently due to inaccurate identification of the base form, namely, confusion between core use and instantial use.¹² For instance, Kunin (1967a: 149–150) registers the PU *cat* with nine lives as an expression created by Shakespeare, quoting:

Tybalt: What wouldst thou have with me?

Mercutio: Good king of cats, nothing but one of your. nine lives; that I mean to make bold withal, and as you shall use me hereafter, dry-beat the rest of the eight.

W. Shakespeare, *Romeo and Juliet*, Act III, Sc.1

On the same page Kunin gives another entry a *cat* has nine lives as a separate PU and gives the following example (op. cit.: 149):

One of the most striking differences between a cat and a. lie is that a cat has Only nine lives.

Mark Twain, Pudd'nhead Wilson

The two forms a cat has nine lives and a cat with nine lives are both registered by Kunin as base forms, i.e., two different entries. However, all the other dictionaries of idioms give only one base form: a cat has nine lives, see Brewer's Dictionary of Phrase and Fable ([1959] 1968: 181), Longman Dictionary of English Idioms (1979: 49), Pickering (1997: 41) and others.

Failure to identify the etymology of the PU:

The etymology of Pus may be one of the causes of lexicographical errors even in very good dictionaries. For instance, the PU to the world's end is given by Kunin's English-Russian Dictionary of Phraseology (Kunin 1967a: 286) as a Shakespearean phrase. However, Chaucer used it five times in its core use in his works¹⁴ (MiE: unto the worldes ende), which was 200 years before Shakespeare! The Oxford English dictionary in XII Volumes ([1933] 1961: 300 of vol. XII) proves that it was already used in the OE period with the preposition *op*: *op sē woruldes ende*. It is crucial to distinguish between a free metaphorical combination of words created by an individual writer (in this case Shakespeare) and a PU – a stable word combination with a figurative meaning and well established in the language tradition.

Sometimes a specific meaning of a phrase is attributed to an author without recognising that the particular instantiation is a case of a well-known PU at the time. For example, Chambers 20th Century Dictionary [1983] 1987 gives the following meanings of colt's tooth: one of a horse's first set of teeth; love of youthful pleasures (Shak.); wantonness. It is imprecise to ascribe this phrase to Shakespeare as the PU **to have a coltes tooth** was used in Chaucer's day (and most probably before him). In Chaucer's works it appears twice, once in core use: CT, A, 3888 and once as an extended metaphor, going beyond the limits of a single sentence:

He was, I trowe, a twenty winter old
And I was fourty, if I shal seye sooth,
But yet I **hadde** alwey a **coltes tooth**.

G a t – t o t h e d 16 I was, and that bicam me weel.

G. Chaucer, The Canterbury Tales, D, 600–603

Failure fully or partly to record instancial use:

Many dictionaries fail to give instantial forms in their illustrations (see Ch. 1). Even those dictionaries that record instantial use in their examples frequently fail to take all the text of the example, leaving part of the instantiation behind, for example Brewer's Dictionary of Phrase and Fable ([1959] 1968: 181) gives the example "Good king of cats, nothing but one of your nine lives" from Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet* as an allusion to a cat has nine lives, leaving out the extension of the PU "dry-beat the rest of the eight". Thus it is an identification error (see Ch. 2.4): "eight of the nine lives" has been left out by the author of the dictionary:

Tybalt: What wouldst thou have with me?

Mercutio: Good king of cats, nothing but one of your nine lives.

W. Shakespeare, *Romeo and Juliet*, Act III, Sc.1

Likewise Kunin's example misses the previous line containing "Tybalt, you ratcatcher". Quoting only half of the instantiation does not bring out the full message. The humiliating rat-catcher is an anaphoric periphrastic extension of the image of the PU. Tybalt is an equally important item; it is part of the extended image, as it contains two meanings (a pun): it is used as a proper name, a nephew to Lady Capulet, and it also has the generic meaning of a common noun, that is, Tybalt was formerly a name commonly given to cats, hence it is linked with the allusion (see Brewer's Dictionary of Phrase and Fable [1959] 1968: 919).

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. For errors in differentiating between core use and instantial use, see Ch. 1.
2. See the explanation in the Preface to Kunin's dictionary (1967b: 12).
3. See Chaucer CT, B, 3828; CT, D, 1455; TC, IV, 1580; TC, V, 894; TC, V, 1058 (Chaucer 1919).
4. For a detailed diachronic study of a colt's tooth, see Whiting (1948).
5. MiE gat-tothed – having the teeth far apart (Skeat 1919: 47).